

snaq_h4; Pseudo-deviance=155052.0

snaq_h3; Pseudo-deviance=155052.0

snaq_h2; Pseudo-deviance=155055.0

snaq_h1; Pseudo-deviance=155068.0

admixtools_h2; Pseudo-deviance=155129.0

admixturetools_h3; Pseudo-deviance=155141.0

phylonet_h1; Pseudo-deviance=155159.0

phylonet_h2; Pseudo-deviance=155167.0

admixtools_h5; Pseudo-deviance=155170.0

snaq_h0; Pseudo-deviance=155175.0

admixtools_h1; Pseudo-deviance=155180.0

raxml_h0; Pseudo-deviance=155220.0

admixtools_h4; Pseudo-deviance=155257.0

phylonet_h0; Pseudo-deviance=155616.0

